

PARC_VKM_Delphi_figures

2024-06-11

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Loading packages

To get the ggsanky package I needed to install a development version from github, which needed devtools.

```
# install.packages("devtools")
#devtools::install_github("davidsjoberg/ggsankey")

library(ggplot2)
library(ggpubr)
library(fitdistrplus)
library(openxlsx)
library(devtools)
library(tidyverse)
library(ggsankey)
```

Get work directory and organise results

```
HOME <- "C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Shanky_Delfi"
setwd(HOME)
```

Create a folder with current date in the Result folder

```
newday <-
file.path('C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Shanky_Delfi/Results',
Sys.Date())
dir.create(newday)
```

Read in data

```
Delphi <-
read_delim("C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Shanky_Delfi/Data/Results_Delp
hi_120624.csv")
```

Data cleaning

Prepare data file for the Sankey plot by changing the name of the content in the columns and the heading of the columns.

```
Delphi$`intermediate` <- if_else(Delphi$`R1 Investigator action` == "Remove  
for agreement", "Included", Delphi$`R1 Investigator action`)  
  
Delphi$`Delphi R1 results` <- if_else(Delphi$`intermediate` == "Round 2",  
"Progress to round 2", Delphi$`intermediate`)  
  
Delphi$`intermediate2` <- if_else(Delphi$`R2 Investigator action` == "Remove  
for agreement", "Included", Delphi$`R2 Investigator action`)  
  
Delphi$`Delphi R2 results` <- if_else(Delphi$`intermediate2` == "Workshop",  
"Progress to workshop", Delphi$`intermediate2`)
```

The next code organise the data to make it suitable as input for ggsankey package, to make the Sankey plot.

```
s1 <- Delphi$Source  
  
s2 <- Delphi$`Bias domain`  
  
s3 <- Delphi$`Delphi R1 results`  
  
s4 <- Delphi$`Delphi R2 results`  
  
s5 <- Delphi$`Workshop results`  
  
  
d <- data.frame(cbind(s1,s2,s3, s4, s5))  
names(d) <- c('Source',  
             'Bias domain',  
             'Delphi R1 results',  
             'Delphi R2 results',  
             'Workshop results')  
  
  
df <- d%>%  
  make_long(Source,  
            `Bias domain`,  
            `Delphi R1 results`,  
            `Delphi R2 results`,  
            `Workshop results`  
  )
```

Make Sankey plots

```
pl <- df %>% drop_na(node) %>% # This removes the NA's before making the
Sankey plot.
  ggplot(aes(x = x,
             next_x = next_x,
             node = node,
             next_node = next_node,
             fill = factor(node),
             label = node))      # This Creates a Label for
each node

pl <- pl + geom_sankey(flow.alpha = 0.5,      #This Creates the
transparency of your node
                      node.color = "black", # This is your node color
                      show.legend = FALSE)  # This determines if you
want your legend to show

pl <- pl + geom_sankey_label(size = 1.5,
                             color = "black",
                             fill = "white") # This specifies the Label
format for each node

pl <- pl + theme(legend.position = 'none')
pl <- pl + theme(axis.title = element_blank(),
                 axis.text.y = element_blank(),
                 axis.ticks = element_blank(),
                 panel.grid = element_blank())

pl <- pl + scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "inferno")

pl
```


Save plot

```
ggsave(filename=file.path(newday, "p1.jpeg"),
        device = NULL,
        width=NA,
        height=NA,
        units="mm")
```